

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE CRITERIA AND THEIR TRAINING TECHNOLOGIES IN TRAINING

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Abstract. *This article discusses the criteria of professional competence of teachers in training, their role and importance in the professional activity of teachers, technologies formation of criteria for the professional competence of teachers in advanced training.*

Keywords. *competence, professional development, teacher, professional-academic, professional-valuable, professional-vocal, effective-active, analytical-reflexive criteria, pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical tasks, level, qualification, skill.*

The socio-economic and political situation in our country has brought about a number of changes in the system of education and training in our modern schools, placing new demands on teachers. This emphasizes the comprehensive improvement of teachers from a professional point of view. Today, the need to train teachers who differ from each other in terms of quality, who can think about the fundamental nature of professional knowledge in a new way, who can solve the problems of education and upbringing with practical-oriented and research methods, is increasing day by day. The need for training at a new level is increasing day by day. In modern conditions, education of the criteria of professional competence of teachers who come for training is one of the fundamental and basic components of professional training of teachers. Improving the system of professional competence of modern teachers arouses interest in the society of pedagogues and society in general. Also, diagnosis of professional competence criteria of teachers in training remains an urgent pedagogical problem.

Studying the criteria of professional competence of teachers in training, analyzing the importance of these criteria in the teacher's activity, developing technologies for training the criteria of professional competence of teachers are important indicators in training the professional competence of teachers. Therefore, what are the criteria of professional competence of teachers in professional development and what is their importance in teacher's activity reflected in?

The following criteria of professional competence of teachers were determined from the experimental work carried out with school teachers who are improving their qualifications in the national centers for training pedagogues in new methods:

- **professional and academic;**
- **professional value;**
- **professional-pronoun;**
- **effective - active;**
- **analytical-reflexive.**

These criteria were determined by the following indicators:

1. Professional knowledge criterion - knowledge of the leading, basic concepts and descriptions of the system of professional knowledge, the concept of education and training, legal

and regulatory documents adopted in the field of education, documents defining the main activities of teachers and students, the laws of education and training, traditional and innovative principles of education, the scope, depth and perfection of knowledge of pedagogical technologies, methods of self-education.

2. Professional-value criterion - treating the teacher's professional competence and professional-pedagogical education as a separate component of the system of cultural and moral values, educating the teacher's professional competence as a means of professional and personal self-improvement.

3. Vocational-pronoun criterion - for the effective performance of the teacher's professional activity, the teacher's professional direction is in harmony with the main directions of his professional competence.

4. Effective-functional criterion - education of general professional skills (predictive, constructive, organizational, communicative, cognitive, reflexive) that make up the core competencies of the teacher - the core of professional competence and determine the effectiveness of professional activity, effective solving of various complex pedagogical situations, modeling of upcoming activity tasks, selection of effective methods, forms, methods and tools of education and upbringing, ownership of various innovative pedagogical technologies.

5. Analytical-reflexive criterion - interest in professional-pedagogical activity, the problem of training the teacher's professional competence, the desire for professional development and self-improvement, professional and professional-educational activity and independence, the presence of the ability to analyze oneself and behavior.

The leading criteria of the professional competence of teachers in professional development are certainly their qualifications and skills in their professional activities. These skills and qualifications are directly reflected in the teacher's professional activity and professional-educational activity.

These criteria of teachers' professional competence are related to the teacher's valuable attitude to his profession, the perfection of the system of professional knowledge and the ability to effectively apply this knowledge in practice, the creation of professional ideals, the increase of the motivation of professional activity, solving complex pedagogical situations in positive ways, and professional development and self-improvement. manifests in his aspirations.

The following educational technologies formed the basis of education of professional competence criteria of teachers in advanced training:

1. Educational technologies aimed at educating the personality of the teacher: integrative technologies, social-educational technologies, technologies that educate the teacher's activity as a social subject.

2. Pedagogical technologies aimed at the humanization of the pedagogical process;

3. Technologies based on the intensification and activity of the teacher's professional activity (active teaching methods): problem-based education (partial research method, educational research technology, research games), project teaching technologies, interactive technologies;

4. Game technologies: pedagogical games, role-playing and imitation games.

The use of technologies for training the criteria of professional competence of teachers in the training of teachers in the team of teachers educates professional knowledge (epistemological component), valuable relationships (value-meaningful component) and special skills (active component) in teachers. Also, the use of interactive and innovative technologies of education,

rather than the traditional teaching methods, in training the criteria of professional competence of teachers in advanced training, in order to increase the interest in independent research and research activities in teachers - it is important to educate a number of professional qualities such as self-education, work on oneself.

REFERENCES

1. Khudoykulov H.J. Modern pedagogical technology is the basis of educational efficiency. - T.: "Navruz", 2013.
2. Aminov A.Kh. Theoretical and practical basis of improving the system of joint training of general secondary education pedagogic staff. Dissertation for the Bachelor of Science in Pedagogical Sciences - T.: 2004. - p. 156.
3. Sokolova S.V. Formirovanie pedagogicheskoy kompetentnosti budushchego prepodavatelya (na primere podgotovki prepodavatelya pedagogicheskix discipline): Diss...k.p.n. - Volgograd, 2004. - 226 p.
4. Mustafoeva D.A., Z.K. Ismailova, "Pedagogical competence of teachers of special subjects in the training system" (on the development of innovative activities). Methodical guide. - Tashkent, TIQXMMI, 2018. p. 37-41.
5. Faizullaeva N. Pedagogical knowledge is the theoretical basis of teacher's professional skills // Lifelong education j. - T.: 2006. No. 6. - p. 102
6. Toraev B.Z., Muqimova G.Kh. Competent approach in education: formation of teacher's professional competence. // Materials of the Republican seminar on the topic "Management and development of personnel resources in the higher education system of Uzbekistan". - T: "Talent" fund, TDPU. 2014. - p.52.